

Synthesis of some 3-Aryl-5-Phthalylrhodanines

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Some 3-aryl-5-phthalylrhodanines have been prepared by a Perkin condensation of phthalic anhydride with the corresponding 3-arylrhodanine at 90° in the presence of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate.

ALTHOUGH phthalic anhydride have been used successfully as the carbonyl component in Perkin reaction¹⁻⁴, its reaction with rhodanines has not been thoroughly investigated. It is reported⁵ that phthalic anhydride reacts with 3-phenylrhodanine in boiling acetic acid to give 3-phenyl-5-phthalylrhodanine (I). In this investigation, we report the synthesis of 3-aryl-5-phthalylrhodanines (I-VIII) in good yields by condensation of phthalic anhydride with the corresponding 3-arylrhodanine in the presence of acetic anhydride and freshly fused sodium

acetate. This method had been used successfully in the preparation of 2-aryl-4-phthalyl-2-oxazolin-5-ones from phthalic anhydride and aroyl glycine⁶. The reaction was carried out by warming the reaction mixture at 90° until the precipitation of the product had ceased. The crude product was separated by filtration and recrystallized from the proper solvent.

The following 3-aryl-5-phthalylrhodanines have been prepared: 3-phenyl-5-phthalylrhodanine (I), 3-(*o*-tolyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (II); 3-(*m*-tolyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (III); 3-(*p*-tolyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (IV); 3-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (V); 3-(*o*-nitrophenyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (VI); 3-(*p*-nitrophenyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (VII); and 3-(*m*-chlorophenyl)-5-phthalylrhodanine (VIII).

- (I) Ar = C₆H₅;
 (II) Ar = *o*-C₆H₄.CH₃;
 (III) Ar = *m*-C₆H₄.CH₃;
 (IV) Ar = *p*-C₆H₄.CH₃;
 (V) Ar = *p*-C₆H₄.O.CH₃;
 (VI) Ar = *o*-C₆H₄.NO₂;
 (VII) Ar = *p*-C₆H₄.NO₂;
 (VIII) Ar = *m*-C₆H₄.Cl.

Experimental

The 3-arylrhodanines were prepared as previously described^{7,8}. Microanalysis were carried out by the microanalytical unit, Cairo University. M.P.s are not corrected.

3-Aryl-5-phthalylrhodanines (I-VIII): A mixture of phthalic anhydride (0.01 mol.) and 3-arylrhodanine (0.01 mol.) dissolved in acetic anhydride (20 ml.) containing freshly fused sodium acetate (0.3 g.) was

TABLE I

TABLE I—PREPARATION OF 3-ARYL-5-PHTHALYLRHODANINES (I-VIII)

3-Phenyl rhodanine	product	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Found %				Calc. %			
					C	H	N	S	C	H	N	S
Unsubst.	I ^a	233-34	71	C ₁₇ H ₉ NO ₃ S ₂	60.3	2.8	4.1	18.5	60.2	2.7	4.1	18.9
2-Methyl-	II ^a	202	73	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₃ S ₂	61.2	3.0	3.8	18.1	61.2	3.1	4.0	18.1
3-Methyl-	III ^b	226	82	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₃ S ₂	61.1	2.9	3.7	18.0	61.2	3.1	4.0	18.1
4-Methyl-	IV ^b	241	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₃ S ₂	61.0	3.1	3.8	18.0	61.2	3.1	4.0	18.0
4-Methoxy-	V ^b	230-31	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ NO ₃ S ₂	58.5	2.9	3.7	17.2	58.5	3.0	3.8	17.3
2-Nitro-	VI ^a	197	84	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	53.0	2.2	7.0	16.6	53.1	2.1	7.3	16.7
4-Nitro-	VII ^b	195	77	C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₂ O ₅ S ₂	53.1	2.2	7.2	16.5	53.1	2.1	7.3	16.7
3-Chloro-	VIII ^a	205	75	C ₁₇ H ₈ ClNO ₃ S ₂	54.6	2.1	3.7	17.0	54.6	2.1	3.7	17.1

a, yellow;

b, orange.

heated on water bath at 90° until the precipitation of the product had ceased (2-4 hr). The reaction mixture cooled, and the precipitated solid was collected by filtration, washed with water (50 ml.). Re-crystallization of the product obtained from acetic acid gave the 3-aryl-5-phthalylrhodanines (I-VIII) with correct elementary analysis (Table 1).

The colour, yield, and m.p.s of compounds I-VIII are given below :

(I) yellow, 71, 233°-34°* ; (II) yellow, 73, 202° ; (III) orange, 82, 226° ; (IV) orange, 76, 241° ; (V)

orange, 74, 230°-31° ; (VI) pale yellow, 84, 197° ; (VII) orange, 77, 195° ; and (VIII) yellow, 75, 205°.

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* Cited⁵ melting point was 234°.